

STUDY OF THE VITAMIN COMPOSITION OF RAPESES SQUEEZE GROWN IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article discusses the issues of studying the fatty vitamin and vitamin composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The fatty vitamin composition of rapeseed squeeze is rich in unsaturated and monounsaturated fatty vitamins, which are not synthesized in the body and come with food. The vitamin composition of rapeseed squeeze was also studied, which indicates that it contains valuable water- and fat-soluble vitamins. The article provides a comparative analysis of the fatty vitamin and vitamin composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarusian selection.*

Keywords: *rapeseed squeeze, vitamin, composition, fatty vitamin, polyunsaturated fatty vitamins, monounsaturated fatty vitamins, biological value, erucic vitamin, tocopherol, choline, oleic vitamin.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps siqmasining yog'da eriydigan vitamin va suvda eriydigan vitamin tarkibini o'rganish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Raps siqmasining vitaminli tarkibi to'yinmagan va mono to'yinmagan vitaminlarga boy bo'lib, ular organizmda sintez qilinmaydi va oziq-ovqat bilan birga keladi. Raps siqmasining vitamin tarkibi ham o'rganildi, bu uning tarkibida suvda va yog'da eriydigan qimmatli vitaminlar mavjudligini ko'rsatadi. Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi va Belarus seleksiyasida yetishtirilgan raps siqmasining vitamin tarkibi qiyosiy tahlil qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raps siqmasi, vitamin, tarkibi, yog'li vitamin, ko'p to'yinmagan yog'li vitaminlar, bir to'yinmagan yog'i eruvchi vitaminlar, biologik qiymat, tokoferol, xolin.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассмотрены вопросы изучения жировой витаминности и витаминности семян рапса, выращиваемого в Республике Узбекистан. Витаминный состав рапса богат ненасыщенными и мононенасыщенными витаминами, которые не синтезируются в организме и поступают с пищей. Изучен также витаминный состав рапса, который показывает, что в нем содержатся ценные водо и жирорастворимые витамины. В статье произведен сравнительный анализ содержания витаминов в семенах рапса, выращенных в селекции Республики Узбекистан и Беларуси.*

Ключевые слова: *рапсовое масло, витамин, состав, жировой витамин, полиненасыщенные жирные витамины, мононенасыщенные жирные витамины, биологическая ценность, токоферол, холин.*

Introduction

Providing the population with food products rich in nutritional and biological value is one of the priority tasks of the state. In order to expand this problem, planting of various crops is expanding, new varieties are being adopted, and non-standard secondary resources are being used so as not to affect the cost of ready-made food products. One of the promising ones in this

direction is rapeseed, which produces an oil with a higher nutritional value than olive oil. Another valuable product is rapeseed squeeze after oil extraction, but there is almost no information about the food safety, physic-chemical composition, nutritional, biological and energy value of rapeseed grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan. no information. This determined the direction of our research. We studied the fat vitamin content and water- and fat-soluble vitamins content of rapeseed oil [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The vitamin composition of oils was determined by gas chromatography on a “Kristall 2000” chromatograph. The oils were prepared for analysis on a chromatograph according to “GOST 30418-96. Vegetable oils. Method for determining fatty vitamins composition.” Oils in an amount of 100 mg were dissolved in hexane (2 ml), 100 µl of ethylation reagent was added, 1 µl of the resulting solution was injected into the chromatograph with a micro syringe. The composition of fatty vitamins was determined using a gas chromatograph. The analysis was carried out using a capillary quartz column HP-5 ms 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm (stationary phase: 5% diphenyl, 95% dimethylsiloxane) from Agilent.

Programming the column thermostat temperature: isotherm 40 °C for 1 min - heating to 210 °C at a rate of 15 °C/min - heating to 150 °C at a rate of 7 °C/min - heating to 280 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min - isotherm 280 °C 10 min.

- Carrier gas: helium, carrier gas rate: 1 ml/min.
- Evaporator temperature 280 °C.
- Ion source temperature 150 °C.
- Quadrupole temperature 230 °C.
- Temperature of the transition chamber is 280 °C.
- Reset 1:10.
- The volume of injected liquid sample is 1 µl.

To identify components, linear retention indices were determined, and the results obtained and the full mass spectrum were compared with object (NIST 2.0 mass spectral objects) and laboratory data [2].

Only components identified by the laboratory with a probability greater than 90% were considered. Quantitative analysis was carried out based on the areas of the corresponding peaks in the chromatogram constructed using the total ion current.

Sampling of rapeseed squeeze was carried out in accordance with GOST 13496.0; preparation of samples of rapeseed squeeze was carried out in accordance with GOST 31218.

Vitamin B1 (thiamine) content is determined by fluorescence intensity measurement method. The essence of the method is to extract vitamin B1 (thiamine) from the analyzed sample of rapeseed squeeze with a solution of sulfuric vitamin, oxidize it with a solution of potassium iron sulfide in thiochrome, extract the oxidized form from the aqueous phase with isobutyl alcohol and measure fluorescence intensity.

The content of vitamin B2 (riboflavin) in the composition of rapeseed squeeze was determined by measuring fluorescence intensity.

The essence of the method is to extract vitamin B2 (riboflavin) from the analyzed rapeseed squeeze sample by vitamin hydrolysis and measure the fluorescence intensity. The contents of vitamins B1 (thiamine) and B2 (riboflavin) in the composition of rapeseed squeeze were determined by high-performance liquid chromatography. The essence of the method is the extraction of vitamins B1 (thiamine) and B2 (riboflavin) from the analyzed sample of rapeseed

squeeze with a solution of hydrochloric vitamin and determination of their content on a liquid chromatograph with a spectrophotometric detector using a reverse-phase elution mode [3].

The content of choline chloride in the composition of rapeseed squeeze was determined by the colorimetric method. The essence of the method is the extraction of choline chloride with distilled water, the formation in the presence of trisodium phosphate, reinecat complex, choline chloride and colorimetric measurement of the color intensity of its acetone solutions. The content of vitamin B5 in the composition of rapeseed squeeze was determined by the colorimetric method.

The essence of the method is the vitamin hydrolysis of bound forms of vitamin B5, purification of the hydrolyzate, obtaining a colored solution and colorimetric determination in comparison with a standard solution. The content of vitamin B5 in the composition of rapeseed squeeze was determined by high-performance liquid chromatography. The essence of the method is the extraction of vitamin B5 from the analyzed sample of rapeseed squeeze with a solution of hydrochloric vitain and the subsequent determination of its content using a liquid chromatograph [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Another indicator of the nutritional and biological value of rapeseed squeeze is the content of water- and fat-soluble vitamins. The next stage of research was to study the content of vitamins in rapeseed squeeze.

The research results are presented in table. 1.

Index	Content in rapeseed squeeze mg/100 g	Content in soybean squeeze mg/100g
Vitamin B1	0,11	0,59
Vitamin B2	0,25	0,25
Choline B4	6,7	Not detected
Pantothenic vitamin B5	42,5	1,92
Vitamin B6	0,05	0,06
Vitamin E	4,4	Not detected
Vitamin PP	11,9	2,5

Analysis of the results of the data in table 1 shows that in rapeseed squeeze the vitamins are represented by groups of fat- and water-soluble vitamins [5]. Secondary raw materials of rapeseed obtained after pressing the oil contain a valuable antioxidant - tocopherol vitamin E - 4.4 mg/100 g and B vitamins, which are contained in a predominant form vitamin B4-6.7 mg/100 g and pantothenic vitamin vitamin B 5 - 42 .5 mg/100 g, vitamin B2 – 0.25 mg/100 g, vitamin B1 – mg/100 g. Soybean squeeze obtained after processing is inferior to rapeseed squeeze. The content of vitamin B5 (pantothenic vitamin) is 22.5% and the content of vitamin PP is 4.76%, and some vitamins such as vitamin B4 (choline), vitamin E are not found in soybean squeeze. The content of vitamins in rapeseed squeeze plays an important role in human life. Thiamine deficiency in humans is manifested by disorders mainly in the muscular and nervous systems. A person experiences fatigue, muscle weakness, and decreased appetite. Sensory impairment, paresthesia and hyperesthesia are observed [6]. Resistance to cold weakens, vitamin deficiency is popularly known as beriberi, and the main clinical sign is polyneuritis. A lack of vitamin B1 in the diet leads to severe disruption of carbohydrate metabolism, especially in brain tissue, where significant increases are observed. Concentrations of pyruvic vitamin. Insufficiency

of vitamin B2 (riboflavin) leads to the appearance of cracked lips and dryness, Cheiloe angular stomatitis, and dermatitis collections. If the vitamin deficiency is significant, conjunctivitis, photophobia appears, anemia of a hypochromic nature develops, and regeneration processes are disrupted. Vitamin B2 is a component of many important oxidative enzymes and is part of flavo proteins in the form of phosphorus esters - flavinonucleotide and flavin adenidine oleotide. Vitamin PP and choline (B4), which are contained in rapeseed squeeze, protect membranes and cells from damage, control cholesterol levels, improve metabolism in nervous tissue, prevent the formation of gallstones, normalize, exchange of rapeseed squeeze promotes the absorption of vegetable protein, so it is necessary for people who do not consume animals, protein participates in carbohydrate metabolism and helps normalize the activity of the gastrointestinal tract. With a lack of vitamin PP in the human diet, diarrhea occurs, replenishment of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity and tongue. Neuritis develops and mental disorders become more severe. Niacin is part of very important coenzymes of tissue respiration and when taken, a specific vascular reaction is observed. The content of niacin is about 11.9 mg/100g in rapeseed squeeze and its addition as added and replacement of part of the cheese with this product leads to enriched vitamin PP. Increasing nutritional and biological value. Rapeseed squeeze has a high choline content of 6.7 mg/100g. It has membrane protective and antiatherosclerotic properties [7]. It is also necessary for the absorption of fat-soluble vitamins A, D, E, K, and the high content of pantothenic vitamin in rapeseed squeeze. When it enters the human body, it is converted into pantothenes, which is part of coenzyme A. Coenzyme A (CoA) plays an important role in the processes of oxidation and acetylation; it is one of the substances in the body involved in the metabolism of proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates. Pantothenic vitamin is required for the metabolism of fats, carbohydrates, amino vitamins, and the synthesis of vital fatty vitamins and cholesterol. vitamins, acetylcholine, hemoglobin. There is also a high content of vitamin E (tocopherol) in rapeseed squeeze. Tocopherols regulate the intensity of free radical reactions in axial cells, prevent the oxidation of unsaturated fatty vitamins in membrane lipids, and influence the biosynthesis of enzymes [8]. With a lack of vitamin A, reproductive functions are disrupted. Damage to the myocardium, vascular and nervous systems is observed. Vitamin E performs not only a vitamin, but also an antioxidant function, therefore it is used for the prevention of cancer, during radiation and chemical effects on the body. It is used for the prevention of coronary heart disease, prostatitis, and decreased sexual activity [9]. Analysis of the vitamin composition of rapeseed squeeze shows that it contains vital vitamins and the quantitative content of some vitamins can satisfy the daily need of the human body for these vitamins. Use as an additive to food products and national dishes of Uzbekistan will contribute to its enrichment. The above vitamins make it possible to increase their biological and nutritional value. For a qualitative analysis of the vitamin composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in Uzbekistan, we compared the data obtained by scientists of the Belarusian University of Food and Chemical Technologies of rapeseed squeeze of Belarusian selection Fig. 1 [10].

Picture 1. Comparative values of the vitamin content in rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarus.

As a comparative analysis of the vitamin composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarusian selection shows, our squeeze has a high content of pantothenic vitamin 42.5 mg/100g and 1.4 mg/100g, which is 32.9%, also a high content of vitamin PP 11, 9 mg/100g per 11.3 mg/100g, choline 6.7 mg/100g per 4.66 mg/100g, vitamin B2 0.25 per 0.04 mg/100g, vitamin B1 0.11 mg/100g per 0.01 mg/100g, vitamin E 4.4 mg/100g, by 4.2 mg/100g, In rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan, only one vitamin is inferior in content to the squeeze of Belarusian selection and this is vitamin B6 0.092 mg/100g by 0.056 mg/100g. This analysis proves that rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan is practically not inferior in vitamin composition to rapeseed squeeze of Belarusian selection, and in some respects, it is higher than rapeseed squeeze of Belarusian selection. The above analysis of the fatty vitamin composition and vitamins of rapeseed squeeze shows that it has high nutritional and biological value and its use as an additive in many food products (sausages, sausages, pasta and other bread products will help enrich the chemical composition, thereby increasing the biological and nutritional value of these dishes and products and does not affect the cost of these products).

CONCLUSION

Presented studies of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan on fatty vitamin and vitamin composition. As a result of the study, new data was obtained on the fatty vitamin and vitamin composition; rapeseed squeeze contains polyunsaturated and monounsaturated fatty vitamins of the ω -3 and ω -6 families containing fatty vitamins that are very valuable and they are not synthesized by the body and must be supplied with food. The content of polyunsaturated fatty vitamins is linolenic (ω -6%), (ω -19.6%). Alpha linolenic (ω -3%) and (ω -8.3%) high content of monounsaturated fatty vitamins – oleic vitamin 62.9% shows the high nutritional value of fatty vitamins of rapeseed squeeze. When studying the vitamin composition, a high content of pantothenic vitamin was determined - 42.5 mg/100g, vitamin PP 11.9 mg/100g, choline 6.7 mg/100g, vitamin E 4.4 mg/100g, which indicates the high biological value of rapeseed squeeze, A comparative analysis of rapeseed squeezes grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarus is also provided, which indicates that it is superior in fatty vitamin and vitamin composition to the Belarusian selection. The practical significance of the research data lies in the fact that new data have been obtained on the fatty vitamin and vitamin

composition of rapeseed squeeze and it will be the basis for the development of additives and fillers from the squeeze to increase the nutritional and biological values of products and national dishes. I would like to note that the introduction as an additive does not affect the cost of these dishes.

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